

Synopsis of how an African Astronomy and an African Nuclear Physics together outline the 'energetic symmetry' of our Universe.

The insights arising from an experiential catholic viewing of the celestial and atomic realms reveals the "energetic symmetry" of our Universe. This in turn indicates the potential we humans have, to create an healing approach to the nuclear issues of our time.

The religious rebellion in 16th Century Europe, known generally as "**The Reformation**", led to the establishment of the Protestant Church, the development of a scientific knowledge of our planetary system, and the physical and chemical nature of elemental matter. This was followed in due course by the virtual discovery of the Atomic World and the development of technologies to extract the energy that is normally locked up in the atoms.

Evidence of the 'energetic symmetry' of our Universe had its beginnings (for me) in the observations of an experiential 'African Astronomy' which sees how the light from the Moon and the light from the Sun combine in the course of a year to create a 'photon'. It is this 'heavenly photon' that in effect lights the Earth with its wholesome blend of "feminine power" and "masculine strength".

The fact that we see the Moon and the Sun as being the same size, and observe that they have the same periods of rotation strongly suggests that the photon effect is a universal phenomenon rather than simply fortuitous.

Meanwhile, an introspective view of family life in general sees how this same photon dynamic (which unifies feminine and masculine forces), is common place amongst us humans and many of the species who populate this planet.

As regards the Atomic World, nuclear physics has determined how there are "four-interactive-forces" in each and every atom. This knowledge in turn allowed for the development of modern-day nuclear technologies, typically the atomic bomb and nuclear reactors.

However, an 'experiential catholic African' view of these 'four forces' recognises that they are equally present and here at work within and between us humans. These four energetic qualities are especially evident in our family lives. In other words, experiential inquiry reveals it is the same energy in the atoms as is here amongst us humans.

This insight then encouraged me to look with social acumen in at the Mushroom Cloud, which appears in the aftermath of every nuclear explosion. Photographs help us see how the copious quantities of energy that the fission process releases out of the atoms, then form, at the speed of Light, the two 'energetic entities', one typically masculine, the other classically feminine, who together create the Mushroom Cloud. With modest prompting, we see them meet with great love and longing for each other.

The sequence of photographs we have of the Mushroom Cloud portray the union, the marriage, of these two 'entities', who are imbued with the same social and spiritual instincts and longings as live and work in us humans. An indication once again of the energetic symmetry that infuses this multi-tiered universal system that we are all within.

I worked at Dounreay, the nuclear reactor here in northern Scotland. In my time there, three insights found a home in me.

The one came from visiting the site laboratory, where I found it possible to experience the feelings of the energy radiating from the spent fuel rods. It was mainly sadness.

A deep hot intense relentless sadness, more profound and disturbing than I could ever imagine. This effect indicates above all else that the atomic particles are sentient, as well as social.

The second insight was largely a consequence of my being born in Kenya, where my father was part of the British administration. Growing up in a colonial household then helped me recognise the imperious attitude of our operations to extract energy from the particle population. I saw how we British, and indeed, all the nuclear nations, are now working in the Atomic World as colonists.

What goes on inside of every reactor is the modern equivalent of the African Slave Trade. History is repeating itself. We Brits in particular, are repeating ourselves.

Meanwhile, I observed how the women on site were entirely familiar with the distressing emotional effect of the radiation coming from the spent fuel. But they were very reluctant to talk about their experience. They stayed quite, stayed mum, because of the misogyny that was established in the hierarchical administration of the reactor. This masculine consciousness focused the interest of the staff always on the physics of the fission process, and any interest or reference to the metaphysics met with indifference or hostility. That was the third insight.

An indigenous catholic experiential mainly-African view of natural phenomena both challenges and compliments our protestant 'white-man's' Western mind with pre-conceptual insight of the parental forces embedded in the light of the Moon and the light of the Sun. Our planet is lit by Her Love and His mix of Light and Gravity.

The same four kinds of energy in the atoms as are here in our humans family lives indicates how atoms are the family systems of the particle population. Our Universe is in effect a system of family systems, the one within the other, the same dynamic as the internally-stacking Russian Dolls display. No wonder we find the same kinds of energy and the same energetic processes at work and play in each dimension of this universal system we are within. This symmetry is not an entirely new observation. The ancient civilisations of Egypt recognised this same principle with the phrase: "As above, so below". The same understanding is becoming known in our time as the "holographic nature of our universe".

This discourse completes by considering how photons are "unit of whole Light", which are in effect "units of universal energy", which are in turn a combination of "feminine power" and "masculine strength". This insight stirs my imagination to think that we humans, we Humanity, have the ability to create photons formed from the four kinds of energy in our family systems: that we might then learn to land these home-made photons amongst the radioactive particles, and determine if this is beneficial for them.

In other words, determine our collective ability to "heal the atom", in contrast to the modern physics-only view of our Western mind which at present only knows how to "split the atom".

I have prepared a more detailed and long-winded 17 page paper that elaborates on this summary account. The paper is entitled: "The insights of an African Astronomy and an African Nuclear Physics reveal the energetic symmetry of our Universe". The paper is parked at this address. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10033207>

Thank you Visitors, for coming by and looking with interest in at what I feel is a rounded and grounded and wholesome way of seeing the Atomic World as the "next floor down" dimension of this shared universal system that we are all within. The atomic particles look to be as full of life and life's longings, the same as ourselves.

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